

USING VISUALIZATION IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

In the article are using of visualization in English lessons analyzed. Information about types of visualization is given.

As a rule, a good visualization must be carefully considered before it can be put into practice. Depending on the situation, this will sometimes be more or less possible.

As with the good old school essay, the first step in preparing a presentation thoroughly is to collect material. So you first collect all potentially useful information on the topic and then, as a second step, select the content that appears essential from the wealth of material available.

In the third step, the content found through the rough selection is further compressed. The following guiding questions could be used for this:

1. What do I want to represent?
2. What is the purpose of the presentation?
3. Who do I want to inform or convince?

Only after this planning work is it about the visualization in the narrower sense of how the planned content is to be presented.

For the production of a visualization, content elements are required, by means of which the information is logically structured. The visual representation is usually an assembly (composition) of different elements. Design elements include:

- Text
- Free graphics and symbols
- Charts

Design element "Text"

As studies have shown, (written) information is most likely to reach the recipient if the following rules are observed:

1. Pay attention to good legibility
 - Pay attention to legibility.
 - choose simple fonts.

- Observe your reading habits.
- Always write from left to right.

Begin the presentation at the top left. Use upper and lower case letters.

2. Note the four “makers of understanding”.

- Simplicity
- Use common words. Make short sentences.
- Outline / order
- Use headings and subheadings.

Form optical blocks.

- Brevity / conciseness
- Limit the statements to the essentials. The art is in the omission!
- Additional stimulant
- use colors; give examples; Use pictures and sketches.

Chart design element

Diagrams are forms of representation for certain facts. Depending on the form of representation, diagrams are used to compare, for example, absolute numbers, development processes or proportions as well as to illustrate inventory sizes, processes and structures.

Examples for this are:

- List and table

They are a good way to make numbers or values transparent.

- Line charts

They are particularly suitable for showing development processes and for comparing processes.

- Column bar charts

They offer the possibility of comparing two or more variables. They show differences in absolute numbers, not trends; they are therefore particularly suitable for comparing values.

- Pie and pie charts

They always represent the whole and its parts.

- Organizational chart / structure and flow chart / network plan

They are used to represent structures and processes. They are suitable for reproducing (complex) relationships.

- Portfolio charts

They are used to display relative sizes and to position the individual objects one below the other. They are often used for market analysis and positioning.

Composition

The design elements text, free graphics, symbols and diagrams are combined on the poster to form a presentation-ready template. In order to achieve the best possible overall presentation, the following points should be considered:

- Sheet splitting
- Logic and arrangement
- Colors and Shapes

Sheet division

In order to achieve a clear structure in the representation, it is first necessary to consider the layout of the sheets. Here it is helpful to divide the poster with a grid, i.e. to halve, third or quarter in width and/or height. The second step is to determine which design elements or parts of them are to be placed in which sub-area.

Arrangement and logic

There are a few basic patterns that can be used as a guide for arranging the design elements within the selected rough grid, these are:

- Symmetry
- Sequence
- Rhythm
- Dynamics

When arranging the design elements, it is important that they are not placed randomly in one way or another, but that the arrangement of the elements

reflects the logical structure of what is to be represented. You can ask yourself this when planning a visualization:

- Should something be presented in its entirety with its components?

suitable is: symmetry / network image

- Should ranks/hierarchy levels be displayed?

suitable is: sequence / organization chart

- Should the causes and their effects be shown?

is suitable: dynamics

- Should things be compared with each other?

is suitable: sequence / column and bar chart / portfolio

Colors and shapes

In addition to what has been said so far, the use of colors and shapes must be carefully planned, because:

Colors and shapes are carriers of meaning

Through a sensible use of colors and shapes:

- important information highlighted,
- clarifies connections,
- Cross-references made between multiple representations

consecutive representations connected to each other.

Summary tips for designing posters

- Only use a few colors per display, but too much color only makes things colorful and can look a bit playful.

- Make the visualization generous. For this reason, long or difficult words as well as too small font sizes are forbidden (see above).

- Build blocks; (also) summarize meaning units by depicting them spatially close to each other.

- Always use the same color and shape for things that belong together in meaning.

- Emphasize what is important, e.g. by using the color red or by framing, underlining or hatching.

- Use open space as a design element; leave enough space.

- Use the stimulating effect of free graphics; draw a little picture too.

Conclusion

Finally, a general recommendation. Please do not forget that the art of visualization does not lie in depicting the wealth of information available, but rather the opposite: The art is in the omission!

In each case, present as much as necessary and as little as possible. It is not the abundance of the offer that is effective, but rather its expressiveness and quality.

REFERENCES:

1. Van Wijk J. J. The value of visualization //VIS 05. IEEE Visualization, 2005. – IEEE, 2005. – C. 79-86.
2. Manovich L. What is visualization //paj: The Journal of the Initiative for Digital. – 2010.
3. қизи Хасанова О. Қ. и др. VISUAL MNEMOTECHNICS //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – C. 372-377.
4. Xasanova O. USING MNEMOTECHNICS IN TEACHING GERMAN ARTICLES FOR UZBEK STUDENTS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.

5. Хасанова О. К. К. ВИДЫ МНЕМОНИКИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ НЕМЕЦКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 40 (124).
6. Турсунова О. С. Применение видеоматериалов в процессе обучения иностранному языку //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 11-2 (144). – С. 76-78.
7. Gulomovna B. G. PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERN TECHNICAL EDUCATION //Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 121-126.